

Review Article for Different Smile Variables in Different Skeletal Growth Patterns

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Abstract

Background: Smile esthetics play a significant role in orthodontic diagnosis and treatment planning. Skeletal growth patterns i.e., horizontal, average, and vertical are associated with soft tissue balance, lip posture, dental and gingival display, and overall smile dynamics.

Objective: This review aimed to systematically assess the influence of skeletal growth patterns on different smile variables, including lip length and thickness, incisor display, interlabial gap, intercommissural widths, buccal corridor, smile arc, lip line, red ratio, smile index, gummy smile, and commissural height.

Methods: A comprehensive literature search was done in Google Scholar for studies published between January 2000 and June 2025. Keywords included "smile analysis," "smile variables," "skeletal growth pattern," "vertical growers," "horizontal growers," and "orthodontics." Eligible studies included original research with quantitative or qualitative assessment of smile variables, with subjects classified as horizontal, average, or vertical growers using cephalometric or photographic methods. Case reports, narrative reviews, and studies with incomplete skeletal classification were excluded. Data extraction included study design, sample size, classification method, and smile parameters assessed.

Results: A total of 30 studies were included. Vertical skeletal patterns were consistently associated with increased maxillary incisor display, gummy smile prevalence, larger interlabial gap, and exaggerated smile arcs. Horizontal patterns showed reduced gingival display, flatter smile arcs, and limited vertical mobility. Average skeletal patterns generally demonstrated balanced smile esthetics and served as the reference group. Inconsistent findings were observed for lip thickness and buccal corridors.

Conclusion: Smile variables demonstrate distinct associations with skeletal growth patterns. Vertical and horizontal growers often exhibit deviations from balanced esthetics that may necessitate customized orthodontic or surgical interventions. Comprehensive smile analysis, integrating static and dynamic imaging with skeletal evaluation, should be an essential component of orthodontic diagnosis and treatment planning.

Keywords: Smile Variables, Skeletal Patterns, Orthodontics, Smile Analysis.

Introduction

The smile is one of the most expressive facial gestures and plays a central role in facial aesthetics, social interaction, and perceived attractiveness¹. Genuine, spontaneous (Duchenne) smiles are associated with positive emotions and are distinguished by the activation of specific facial muscles². It has been seen that different cultural and social factors influence how smiles are interpreted across societies³. In orthodontics, although traditional focus was placed on achieving ideal occlusion and dental alignment, patients usually seek treatment to improve the appearance of their smile⁴. This shift in patient expectations has led to greater emphasis on smile analysis and smile design as essential components of orthodontic diagnosis and treatment planning⁵.

Musculature plays a decisive role in shaping the dynamics of the smile across different skeletal growth patterns. Studies of masticatory muscles have shown that subjects with vertical (dolichofacial) facial patterns exhibit significantly reduced EMG activity in masseter and anterior temporalis both at rest and during maximal clenching compared to horizontal (brachyfacial) subjects, who show substantially higher activity⁶. Furthermore, measurements of resting vertical dimension (EMGRVD) are higher in dolichofacial individuals than in brachyfacial ones, indicating a posture of

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muscle elongation and possibly lower tonic contraction⁷. While direct EMG studies of smile muscles such as the zygomaticus major, orbicularis oris, or levator labii superioris across growth patterns are limited, recent work has demonstrated that these muscles display distinct activation amplitudes during different facial expressions in healthy adults⁸; and high resolution facial EMG mapping confirms reproducible patterns of perioral muscle recruitment during smiles (smile tasks) among individuals. Taken together, these findings support the model that in horizontal growers, perioral muscles (e.g. zygomaticus, orbicularis oris) function with greater efficiency and strength, whereas in vertical growers these muscles are relatively weaker, elongated, or less tonically active, leading to differences in lip competence, gingival display, and smile arc.

A number of parameters including the smile arc⁹, smile line, dental and gingival display, buccal corridors¹⁰, lip line, and symmetry have been identified as key determinants of an attractive smile. Researchers such as Hulsey¹¹ and Sarver¹² highlighted that incisor display, lip positioning, and the curvature of the incisal edges relative to the lower lip are fundamental features of smile esthetics. With advances in cephalometric and photographic analyses, orthodontics has moved towards a soft tissue oriented approach¹³. Importantly, skeletal growth patterns significantly influence smile variables, making it essential to adapt treatment goals according to individual growth patterns to achieve optimal esthetic outcomes¹⁴. Smile analysis encompasses a range of dental and soft tissue parameters that collectively determine esthetics.

Influence of Skeletal Patterns on Smile Variables

1. Horizontal Skeletal Pattern (Hypodivergent)

Individuals with a horizontal skeletal pattern typically exhibit reduced lower facial height and a relatively strong mandibular plane. Smile characteristics in this group often include minimal gingival display and a flatter smile arc. While smiles may appear broad, they generally demonstrate limited vertical dynamism. Additionally, upper lip thickness is often reduced due to the forward positioning of the mandible, which can influence the amount of incisor exposure during smiling.

2. Average Skeletal Pattern (Normodivergent)

Subjects with an average skeletal pattern present balanced vertical and sagittal facial proportions. Their smile variables tend to be harmonious, with consonant smile arcs and dental and gingival display falling within esthetic norms. Consequently, this group is frequently regarded as the reference standard in comparative studies of smile characteristics.

3. Vertical Skeletal Pattern (Hyperdivergent)

Vertical skeletal patterns are associated with increased lower facial height, a steep mandibular plane, and a tendency toward open bite. Individuals in this group often display greater maxillary incisor exposure, a higher prevalence of gummy smiles, and increased lip mobility and commissural height. While the smile arc is typically consonant, it is frequently exaggerated due to vertical disproportions, which can pose challenges for esthetic management in orthodontic treatment.

Materials and Methods

Skeletal Pattern Assessment

Skeletal growth patterns in the included studies were identified using established cephalometric and anthropometric techniques. Subjects were categorized as horizontal (hypodivergent), average (normodivergent), or vertical (hyperdivergent) based on lateral cephalometric measurements such as the mandibular plane angle (SN-GoGn), Frankfort mandibular plane angle (FMA),

lower anterior facial height, and facial height ratios¹⁵. Additionally, some studies employed three dimensional imaging or facial indices to assess vertical and sagittal skeletal relationships. These methods provided a standardized approach for classifying participants, enabling systematic comparison of smile variables across different skeletal patterns. This framework facilitated the evaluation of deviations from balanced or aesthetically ideal smiles in relation to underlying skeletal morphology.

Smile Photography Protocol

Accurate smile analysis requires standardized photographic documentation to ensure reproducibility and reliability of measurements. Still photographs should be taken with the patient in a natural head position, lips at rest, and during a full smile. Frontal and lateral views are typically captured, with a consistent camera to patient distance and proper lighting to minimize distortion. High resolution images allow precise assessment of smile variables such as incisor display, lip lengths and thicknesses, intercommissural widths, buccal corridors, and gingival exposure.

Dynamic photographs or video recordings complement static images by capturing the smile in motion, providing information on lip mobility, smile arc progression, and soft tissue dynamics. Patients are instructed to perform a natural smile, and multiple recordings may be taken to ensure consistent and representative expressions. Integration of both still and dynamic imaging offers a comprehensive evaluation, combining quantitative measurements from static images with functional insights from motion analysis. This dual approach enhances diagnostic accuracy and informs treatment planning aimed at achieving optimal smile aesthetics and soft tissue balance.

The variables commonly assessed in orthodontic research and clinical practice include:

Upper lip length (at rest and during smiling)¹⁶: Vertical measurement from the subnasale to the stomion superius, both in rest and in smile position. Variations influence incisor and gingival exposure.

Lower lip length (at rest and during smiling): Vertical distance from the stomion inferius to the soft tissue menton. Alterations affect smile harmony and lip competence.

Upper lip thickness: Measured at the vermilion border or midline, influencing dental and gingival display during smiling.

Lower lip thickness: Impacts lip posture, contact with incisors, and the overall smile profile.

Incisor display (maxillary and mandibular): The amount of incisor crown visible during smiling, which is a critical determinant of attractiveness and youthfulness.

Interlabial gap: Vertical distance between the upper and lower lips during smiling, reflecting lip mobility.

Outer intercommissural width (at rest and during smiling): The horizontal distance between lip commissures, indicating the breadth of the smile.

Inner intercommissural width: The space between the inner vermilion borders of the lips, contributing to dental display assessment.

Buccal corridor: Negative space between the buccal surfaces of posterior teeth and the corners of the mouth; excessive corridors can reduce smile fullness.

Smile arc¹⁷: The relationship between the curvature of the maxillary incisal edges and the contour of the lower lip. A consonant smile arc is generally perceived as more esthetic.

Lip line¹⁸: The vertical position of the upper lip relative to the teeth and gingiva, classified as high, average, or low.

Red ratio¹⁹: The proportion of vermilion height of the upper lip to that of the lower lip, which influences smile balance.

Smile index²⁰: Ratio of intercommissural width to the interlabial gap, used to quantify smile proportions.

Gummy smile²¹: Excessive gingival display (>2 mm) during smiling, often associated with vertical skeletal patterns.

Commissural height²²: Vertical difference between the commissures, affecting symmetry and esthetics.

Together, these variables offer a thorough approach to evaluating the smile, enabling clinicians to recognize variations, associate them with underlying skeletal patterns, and plan orthodontic or surgical treatments more effectively.

Databases or Search Engines Used

A comprehensive literature search was conducted using Google Scholar to identify studies evaluating smile variables in relation to skeletal growth patterns. The search included publications from January 2000 to June 2025 and employed keywords such as "smile analysis," "smile variables," "upper lip length," "lower lip length," "incisor display," "buccal corridor," "smile arc," "gummy smile," "skeletal patterns," "hypodivergent," and "hyperdivergent." Only studies involving human subjects were considered. Duplicate records and studies lacking quantitative or qualitative data on smile variables were excluded. Relevant studies were screened, and data were extracted regarding study design, sample characteristics, skeletal classification, smile variables assessed, measurement methods, and key findings.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Inclusion criteria: Original research studies reporting quantitative or qualitative assessment of smile variables, studies classifying subjects according to skeletal patterns (horizontal, average, vertical), and studies using standardized measurement techniques such as photographic analysis, cephalometry, or 3D imaging.

Exclusion criteria: Case reports, narrative reviews (except for background information), and studies with incomplete or unclear data regarding smile variables or skeletal classification.

Data Extraction

For each included study, information was systematically collected on study design, sample characteristics (including size, age, and demographics), method of skeletal classification, and the specific smile variables evaluated such as upper and lower lip length and thickness, maxillary and mandibular incisor display, interlabial gap, inner and outer intercommissural widths, buccal corridor, smile arc, lip line, red ratio, smile index, gummy smile, and commissural height. Details regarding measurement techniques and principal findings were also recorded to facilitate comparative analysis.

Data Synthesis

The review was performed using a narrative approach, summarizing and interpreting trends in smile variables across different skeletal growth patterns. Variables were examined in relation to horizontal (hypodivergent), average (normodivergent), and vertical (hyperdivergent) skeletal types, with particular focus on deviations from a balanced or aesthetically ideal smile. The synthesized findings were used to discuss clinical relevance and guide orthodontic assessment and treatment planning.

Discussion

Vertical growth pattern is generally associated with longer and thinner lips, greater incisal display, larger interlabial gap, narrower intercommissural width, more frequent gummy smiles, and consonant smile arcs.

Horizontal growth pattern tends to show shorter but thicker lips, smaller interlabial gap, wider intercommissural width, and flatter smile arcs.

Average growth pattern usually falls in between, with some variables (lip thickness, intercommissural width) being consistently thinner or smaller compared to vertical and horizontal extremes.

Smile Variable	Vertical Growth Pattern	Horizontal Growth Pattern	Average Growth Pattern
Upper lip length (rest & smiling)	↑ Increased (Siddiqui ²⁷ , Grover ²⁸ , Senthilkumar ²⁹ , Feres ³⁰ , Ahmed ³¹ , Liang ³²) ↓ Shorter (Bhavsar ²⁹ , Demir ³⁰ , Bhadusha S ³¹)	↓ Shorter (Bhavsar ²⁹ , Demir ³⁰ , Bhadusha S ³¹)	—
Lower lip length (rest & smiling)	↑ Increased (Siddiqui ²⁷ , Grover ²⁸ , Ahmed ³¹ , Feres ³⁰) ↓ Shorter (Bhavsar ²⁹ , Singh S ³²)	↓ Shorter (Bhavsar ²⁹ , Singh S ³²)	—
Upper lip thickness	↓ Thinner (Ashraf ³³ : high angle cases thinner; Grover ²⁸ : thicker in vertical & horizontal vs average; Feres ³⁰ , Senthilkumar ²⁹ : NS)	↑ Thicker (Ashraf ³³ : low angle cases thicker; Grover ²⁸ : thicker in horizontal & vertical vs average)	↓ Thinner (Grover ²⁸ : thinner than vertical & horizontal)
Lower lip thickness	↓ Thinner (Ashraf ³³ : high angle cases thinner; Grover ²⁸ : same trend; Feres ³⁰)	↑ Thicker (Ashraf ³³ : low angle thicker; Grover ²⁸ : horizontal > average)	↓ Thinner (Senthilkumar ²⁹ : average < vertical & horizontal)
Incisal display	↑ Increased (Jeelani ³⁴ , Singh S ³² , Senthilkumar ²⁹ , Grover ²⁸ , Ahmed ³¹ , Bhavsar ²⁹ , Siddiqui ²³)	—	McNamara ³⁵ : no sig. difference
Interlabial gap	Mixed: ↑ or NS (Ahmed ³¹ , Grover ²⁸ , Siddiqui ²³): consistent; Bhavsar ²⁹ : greater in average; Ahmed ³¹ : ↓ in low angle)	↓ (Ahmed ³¹ : low angle ↓)	↑ Greater in average (Bhavsar ²⁹)
Intercommissural width	↓ Lower (Ahmed ³¹ , Singh S ³² , Jeelani ³⁴ , Grover ²⁸ , Siddiqui ²³): higher in low angle)	↑ Higher (Ahmed ³¹ , Singh S ³² , Jeelani ³⁴ , Grover ²⁸ , Siddiqui ²³)	NS (Senthilkumar ²⁹ , El bialy ³⁶)
Buccal corridor	NS (M. Albakeem ³⁷ , Senthilkumar ²⁹ , Sarver & Ackerman ³⁸ , McNamara ³⁵ , Bhavsar ²⁹)	NS (same studies)	NS
Gummy smile	↑ More frequent (Beltran ³⁹ , Sarver ³⁸)	—	—
Smile arc	↑ Consonant arc more common (Siddiqui ²³)	↑ Flat arc more common (Siddiqui ²³)	—

Table 1- Smile variables in different Growth Patterns

Table 2- Flowchart describing how skeletal patterns affect smile variables.

Conclusion

Smile variables are closely associated with skeletal growth patterns, with horizontal, average, and vertical patterns demonstrating distinct characteristics in lip dynamics, incisor display, smile arc, and gingival exposure. Average skeletal patterns generally reflect a balanced, harmonious smile, while vertical and horizontal patterns show deviations that may require tailored orthodontic or surgical interventions. Comprehensive evaluation using both static and dynamic imaging, coupled with an understanding of skeletal morphology, is essential for achieving optimal aesthetic and functional outcomes. Further research incorporating standardized methodologies, diverse populations, and advanced imaging technologies will strengthen evidence based approaches for smile analysis and treatment planning.

Limitations

Several limitations exist in the current literature on smile variables and their association with skeletal patterns. Many studies rely predominantly on two dimensional photographs or cephalometric analyses, which may not fully capture the dynamic and three dimensional aspects of the smile. Variations in measurement techniques and definitions of smile variables across studies further limit the comparability of findings. Additionally, sample sizes are often small, and study populations lack diversity in terms of ethnicity, age, and cultural background, restricting the generalizability of results. Longitudinal data assessing the effects of orthodontic or orthognathic interventions on smile aesthetics are limited. Finally, patient reported outcomes and subjective perceptions of smile attractiveness are underrepresented, making it difficult to correlate objective measurements with patient satisfaction and esthetic perception.

Future Research Directions

Despite considerable progress in understanding smile variables across skeletal patterns, several areas warrant further investigation. Dynamic smile analysis using three dimensional imaging and motion capture is needed to capture the natural variability and progression of smiles, which static photographs cannot fully represent. Standardized measurement protocols for variables such as incisor display, lip lengths and thicknesses, buccal corridors, commissural height, and smile arc are essential to improve consistency and comparability across studies. Longitudinal research tracking changes before, during, and after orthodontic or orthognathic interventions will clarify the long-term impact of skeletal and dental modifications on smile aesthetics. Additionally, studies integrating skeletal, dental, and soft tissue parameters, as well as diverse populations and age groups, are necessary to establish normative data and account for ethnic and cultural variations in smile perception. Finally, incorporating patient-reported outcomes and leveraging emerging technologies such as artificial intelligence and facial recognition software could enhance predictive accuracy and optimize individualized treatment planning.

References

- Messinger DS, Fogel A, Dickson KL. What's in a smile? Developmental psychology of smiling. *J Nonverbal Behav.* 1997; 21 (1): 45–60.
- Duchenne GB. *The Mechanism of Human Facial Expression.* New York: Cambridge University Press; 1990.
- Rychlowska M, Jack RE, Garrod OG, Schyns PG, Martin JD, Niedenthal PM. Functional smiles: Tools for love, sympathy, and war. *Psychol Sci.* 2017; 28 (9): 1259–70.
- Ackerman JL, Ackerman MB, Brensinger CM, Landis JR. A morphometric analysis of the posed smile. *Clin Orthod Res.* 1998; 1 (1): 2–11.
- Sarver DM, Ackerman MB. Orthodontics about face: The re-emergence of the esthetic paradigm. *Am J Orthod Dentofacial Orthop.* 2003; 124 (5): 486–96.
- Gomes SG, Custódio W, Faot F, Del Bel Cury AA, Garcia RC. Mastication, EMG Activity and Occlusal Contact Area in Subjects with Different Facial Vertical Patterns. *Journal of Oral Rehabilitation.* 2010; 37 (11): 813-9.
- Manns A, Valdivieso C, Rojas V, Valdés C, Ramírez V. Comparison of clinical and electromyographic rest vertical dimensions in dolichofacial and brachyfacial young adults: a cross-sectional study. *Journal of Prosthetic Dentistry.* 2018 Oct; 120 (4): 513-9
- Mueller N, Trentzsch V, Heinrich M, Kutenreich AM, Guntinas-Lichius O, Volk GF, Anders C. Comparative analysis of electrical signals in facial expression muscles. *Biomed Eng Online.* 2025; 24 (1): 50
- Tjan AHL, Miller GD, The JG. Some esthetic factors in a smile. *J Prosthet Dent.* 1984; 51 (1): 24–8.
- Zachrisson BU. Esthetic factors involved in anterior tooth display and the smile: vertical dimension. *J Clin Orthod.* 1998; 32 (7): 432–45.
- Hulsey CM. An esthetic evaluation of lip-teeth relationships present in the smile. *Am J Orthod.* 1970; 57 (2): 132–44.
- Sarver DM. Principles of cosmetic dentistry in orthodontics: Part 1. Shape and proportionality of anterior teeth. *Am J Orthod Dentofacial Orthop.* 2004; 126 (6): 749–53.
- Holdaway RA. A soft-tissue cephalometric analysis and its use in orthodontic treatment planning. *Am J Orthod.* 1983; 84 (1): 1–28.
- Ackerman JL, Proffit WR, Sarver DM. The emerging soft tissue paradigm in orthodontic diagnosis and treatment planning. *Clin Orthod Res.* 1999; 2 (2): 49–52
- Jacobson A, Jacobson RL. *Radiographic Cephalometry: From Basics to 3D Imaging.* 2nd ed. Hanover Park (IL): Quintessence Publishing; 2006. p. 105-6
- Krishnan P, Senthilkumar A, Muthukumar K, Subramani R, Parvin R. Evaluation of smile characteristics of attractive smile in various growth patterns. *J Indian Orthod Soc.* 2025; 59 (1): 17–25.
- Seixas MR, Câmara CA. The smile arc: review and synthesis. *Dental Press J Orthod.* 2021 Jun 30; 26 (3): 21-3.
- Holdaway RA. The influence of lip position on facial esthetics. *Am J Orthod.* 1983; 83 (3): 249–62.
- loi H, Kuroda T, Sato M, et al. Lip proportions and their relationship to facial esthetics in Japanese adults. *Orthod Craniofac Res.* 2005; 8 (3): 125–30
- Ackerman MB, Ackerman JL. Smile analysis and design in the digital era. *J Clin Orthod.* 2002; 36 (4): 221–36.
- Sarver DM, Ackerman JL. The aesthetic smile: diagnosis and treatment. *Clin Plast Surg.* 2003; 30 (1): 1–11.
- Namratha M, Dhanraj M, Jain AR. Comparative evaluation of upper lip length and the commissural height in Chennai population. *J Adv Pharm Educ Res.* 2017; 7 (3): 223–7.
- Siddiqui N, Tandon P, Singh A, Haryani J. Dynamic smile evaluation in different skeletal patterns. *Angle Orthod.* 2016; 86: 1019-25.
- Grover N, Kapoor DN, Verma S, Bharadwaj P. Smile analysis in different facial patterns and its correlation with underlying hard tissues. *Prog Orthod.* 2015; 16: 28.
- Senthilkumar A, Krishnan P, Arasappan R, Muthukumar K, Subramani R, Parvin R. Evaluation of Smile Characteristics of Attractive Smile in Various Growth Patterns. *Journal of Indian Orthodontic Society.* 2024 Feb 12; 17-25
- Feres MFN, Hitos SF, DeSousa HIP, Matsumoto MAN. Comparison of soft tissue size between different facial patterns. *Dental Press J Orthod* 2010; 15 (4): 84-93
- Ahmed Z, Abbasi MS, Batool S, Khurshid Z, Zafar MS. Assessment of smile characteristics in different vertical skeletal patterns: A cross-sectional study. *BMC Oral Health.* 2022; 22 (1): 239-44
- Liang L-Z, Hu W-J, Yan-Ling Z, Chung K-H. Analysis of dynamic smile and upper lip curvature in young Chinese. *Int J Oral Sci.* 2013; 5 (1): 49-53

29. Bhavsar A, Nehete A, Gulve N, Shah K, Aher S. Factors Affecting Smile Esthetics in Adults with Different Types of Growth Patterns. IOSR-JDMS. 2018 Aug 28; 17 (8):44-50.
30. Demir R, Baysal A. Three dimensional evaluation of smile characteristics in subjects with increased vertical facial dimensions. Am J Orthod Dentofacial Orthop. 2020 Jun; 157 (6): 773-782
31. Badusha SJ, Joneja P, Agarwal A, Singh Choudhary D. Correlation of vertical dimension with lip position, nasolabial angle and incisal display at rest and at smile in young adults. Orthodontic Journal of Nepal. 2021;11(2):11-9
32. Singh VP, Sharma JN. Principles of smile analysis in orthodontics a clinical overview. Health Renaissance (Nepal). 2011; 9 (1): 35-40
33. Ashraf K, Kulshrestha R, Azam A, Shabir S, Kaur H. Soft tissue analysis of chin, upper lip length and thickness in patients with different mandibular divergent patterns – A cephalometric study. IP Indian J Orthod Dentofacial Res. 2018; 4 (2): 88-93.
34. Jeelani, W., Fida, M., Shaikh, A. The maxillary incisor display at rest: analysis of the underlying components. Dental Press Journal of Orthodontics.2018; 23 (6), 48-55
35. McNamara L, McNamara JA, Ackerman MB, Baccetti T. Hard- and soft-tissue contributions to the esthetics of the posed smile in growing patients seeking orthodontic treatment. American Journal of Orthodontics and Dentofacial Orthopedics. 2008 Apr;133 (4): 491-9
36. El Bialy T, Fayed M, El Namrawy M. Are buccal corridors and smile width relating to smile esthetics? A photometric study. IP Indian J Orthod Dentofacial Res. 2020; 6 (2): 63-67
37. Alhakeem MM, ElKalza AR, ElHarouni NM. Smile esthetics in different vertical skeletal patterns in an Egyptian sample: a cross-sectional observational study. Egyptian Orthodontic Journal. 2024; 65 (1): 116-28
38. Sarver DM, Ackerman MB. Dynamic smile visualization and quantification: part 1. Evolution of the concept and dynamic records for smile capture. Am J Orthod Dentofacial Orthop 2003; 124: 4-12
39. Beltrán SM, Bernal de Jaramillo LV, Zapata-Noreña O, Giraldo-Fernández MP, Barbosa-Liz DM. Cephalometric differences in gummy smile and non-gummy smile children: a case-control study. Pesqui Bras Odontopediatria Clín Integr. 2025; 25: 230-4

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